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Research Article

**RELATIONSHIP OF HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE AND HEART
STROKE AMONG LOCAL POPULATION OF PAKISTAN**Dr. Ameer Hamza¹, Dr. Muhammad Ahsan¹, Dr. Muhammad Junaid¹¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: High blood pressure (HBP) is a leading major risk factor for chronic diseases and deaths. The prevalence of patients with high blood pressure (HT) had reached from 600 million in 1980 to one billion in 2008.

Objectives of the study: The main objective of the study is to find the relationship of high blood pressure and heart stroke among local population of Pakistan. **Methodology of the study:** This cross-sectional study was conducted at Jinnah Hospital Lahore during March 2019 to November 2019. This study was conducted according to the rules and regulations of ethical committee of hospital. This research will help towards next findings of effect of blood pressure in high blood pressure and cardiovascular diseases. **Results:** The data shows that there is a significant relationship between high blood pressure and CVD. There is also some positive relationship between socio-economic status and high blood pressure with respect to CVD. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, Increase in number of deaths due to cardiovascular diseases in recent years diverted researchers' attention to prevention and controlling of HBP which is a leading cause of cardiovascular diseases.

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INTRODUCTION:

High blood pressure (HBP) is a leading major risk factor for chronic diseases and deaths. The prevalence of patients with high blood pressure (HT) had reached from 600 million in 1980 to one billion in 2008.¹ The prevalence of HBP was approximately 40% among adults of 25 years and above in 2008. Approximately 7.5 million people (12.8% of all-cause deaths) die every year due to HBP. It is estimated that HT is responsible for 45% of deaths due to heart diseases and 51% of deaths due to stroke. HBP consists of 3.7% of Disability Adjusted Life Years¹. Even prehigh blood pressure (PreHT) increases mortality risk due to cardiovascular and stroke-related diseases.

High blood pressure is a significant public health problem, with a worldwide prevalence of 40.8% and a control rate of 32.3. High blood pressure is a noteworthy hazard factor for various genuine health conditions, including cardiovascular ailment, cerebrovascular malady, and constant kidney illness¹. Worldwide, 9.4 million passing are credited to difficulties from high blood pressure, including 45% of all passing because of coronary vein illness and 51% of all passing because of stroke². These relations are steady in the two people, in youthful, moderately aged, and more seasoned subjects, among different racial and ethnic gatherings, and inside and between nations. In spite of the fact that there is a continuum of cardiovascular hazard crosswise over levels of circulatory strain, the characterization of grown-ups as indicated by pulse gives a system to differentiating levels of hazard related with different circulatory strain classes and for characterizing treatment edges and helpful objectives³.

Elevated blood pressure (BP) is a causal risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD). In addition, randomized clinical trials among people with high blood pressure have illustrated, in total, a decrease in CVD occasions by 20%, coronary illness (CHD)

by 17%, stroke by 27%, and heart disappointment by 28% for each 10 mm Hg systolic BP (SBP) bringing down with medicinal treatment. In this manner, counteractive action, location, treatment, and control of lifted BP, and its clinical connect high blood pressure, is a critical general health need and an essential focus for CVD aversion⁸.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to find the relationship of high blood pressure and heart stroke among local population of Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Jinnah Hospital Lahore during March 2019 to November 2019. This research will help towards next findings of effect of blood pressure in high blood pressure and cardiovascular diseases. The data was collected from 100 patients which was suffering from high blood pressure and any kind of heart issue. We collect the data in two sections, as first of all we collect some demographic information regarding age, sex, socio-economic status and history of blood pressure. Then in second part we collect data regarding high blood pressure and heart issues. For this purpose, we prepare a questionnaire and fill that from patients.

Statistical analysis

Two-way ANOVA was performed to study the contributions. A chi-square test was used to examine the difference in the distribution of the fracture modes (SPSS 19.0 for Windows, SPSS Inc., USA).

RESULTS:

The data shows that there is a significant relationship between high blood pressure and CVD. There is also some positive relationship between socio-economic status and high blood pressure with respect to CVD. Table 01 shows the values of use of drug and other factors.

Table 01: Statistical analysis values of Control group and diseased group

Characteristics	Current blood pressure level			
	Normal	PreHT	HT	Total
HT medication	n (%)^a	n (%)^a	n (%)^a	n (%)^b
Using regular	94 (22.9)	188 (45.9)	128 (31.2)	410 (84.5)
Using irregular	11 (14.7)	36 (48.0)	28 (37.3)	75 (15.5)
HT training	$X^2 = 2.80 P = 0.247$			
Not received	73 (23.4)	140 (44.9)	99 (31.7)	312 (64.3)
Received	32 (18.5)	84 (48.6)	57 (32.9)	173 (35.7)
Alternative or complementary medicine	$X^2 = 1.61 P = 0.447$			
Not admitted	65 (22.4)	126 (43.4)	99 (34.1)	290 (59.8)
Admitted	40 (20.5)	98 (50.3)	57 (29.2)	195 (40.2)
Exercise level	$X^2 = 2.24 P = 0.327$			
Not exercising	52 (20.6)	116 (46.0)	84 (33.3)	252 (52.0)
Inadequate	17 (21.0)	40 (49.4)	24 (29.6)	81 (16.7)
Adequate	36 (23.7)	68 (44.7)	48 (31.6)	152 (31.3)
Fruit and vegetable consumption	$X^2 = 0.96 P = 0.916$			
Not eat every day	23 (20.4)	51 (45.1)	39 (34.5)	113 (23.3)
One meal per day	19 (18.1)	55 (52.4)	31 (29.5)	105 (21.6)
Two meals per day	17 (18.9)	35 (38.9)	38 (42.2)	90 (18.6)
≥ 3 meals per day	46 (26.0)	83 (46.9)	48 (27.1)	177 (36.5)
Salt consumption habits	$X^2 = 9.17 P = 0.164$			
Normal/more salty	47 (24.2)	84 (43.3)	63 (32.5)	194 (40.0)
Less salty	33 (19.8)	81 (48.5)	53 (31.7)	167 (34.4)
Salt less	25 (20.2)	59 (47.6)	40 (32.3)	124 (25.6)
How to continue BP	$X_2 = 1.61 p = 0.807$			
Normal	84 (25.8)	163 (50.0)	79 (24.2)	326 (67.2)
High	11 (8.7)	43 (34.1)	72 (57.1)	126 (26.0)
Unstable	10 (30.3)	18 (54.5)	5 (15.2)	33 (6.8)
HT duration	$X_2 = 52.69 P < 0.001$			
< 5 years	33 (21.0)	69 (43.9)	55 (35.0)	157 (32.4)
5–9 years	38 (31.7)	47 (39.2)	35 (29.2)	120 (24.7)
10–14 years	20 (20.4)	46 (46.9)	32 (32.7)	98 (20.2)
≥ 15 years	14 (12.7)	62 (56.4)	34 (30.9)	110 (22.7)
	$X_2 = 14.43 p = 0.025$			
Total	105 (21.6)	224 (46.2)	156 (32.2)	485 (100.0)

Ref: MahmutKilic et al., 2016

DISCUSSION:

There are some limitations to our study. Firstly, the study population consisted of residents in Pakistan. Secondly, the study enrolled only subjects from primary health centers, thus the data in hand can't reflect hypertensive subjects applied to secondary or tertiary health centers. Thirdly, this is a cross-sectional study based on claims of subjects, thus the answers of subjects may be biased⁸.

Our approach to understand disease development in early life, identify key pathways of interest in predisposition to high blood pressure and develop specific preventive approaches has been to use multi-modality imaging to capture information on cardiovascular structure and function 'from heart to capillary'⁹. With this approach it becomes possible

to model the interrelationship between features of the cardiovascular system and, with longitudinal data, study the progression of disease across vessel and heart. By extending the data collection to other organs such as brain and liver, a holistic view of disease development can be captured¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, Increase in number of deaths due to cardiovascular diseases in recent years diverted researchers' attention to prevention and controlling of HBP which is a leading cause of cardiovascular diseases

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